

RESEARCH ARTICLE

REVISED Post-trial access practice in malaria, tuberculosis, and NTDs clinical trial studies across Sub-Saharan African countries, A quantitative study

[version 2; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 1 not approved]

Yemisrach Seralegne^{1,2}, Cynthia Khamala Wangamati²,
Rosemarie de la Cruz Bernabe ², Ibrahim Mdala³, Martha Zewdie¹,
Hawult Taye Adane ¹

¹Clinical trial unit, Armauer Hansen Research Institute, Addis Ababa, 1005, Ethiopia²Centre for Medical Ethics, Institute of Health and Society, Faculty of Medicine, University of Oslo, Norway, Oslo, 0450, Norway³Department of General Practice, Institute of Health and Society, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway, Oslo, 0450, Norway

v2 First published: 07 Oct 2024, 4:212
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18175.1>
Second version: 07 Mar 2025, 4:212
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18175.2>
Third version: 25 Apr 2025, 4:212
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18175.3>
Latest published: 23 Jun 2025, 4:212
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18175.4>

Abstract

Background

According to the Council of International Organizations and Medical Sciences (CIOMS) 2016, post-trial access (PTA) refers to the ethical imperative that requires the sponsor, researchers, and relevant public health authority, "to make available as soon as possible any intervention or product developed, and knowledge generated, for the population or community in which the research is carried out."

PTA is stipulated and recommended by different international research guidelines like CIOMS, and it was acknowledged that PTA should be accessible to those who actively participated in the trial study and the community and/or host country. Law, policy, and practical guidance for PTA has so far been vague but has recently attracted and increased attention in the context of benefit sharing of scientific research results with low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Even though the number of clinical trials conducted in the Sub-

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 4 (revision) 23 Jun 2025			 view
version 3 (revision) 25 Apr 2025			
version 2 (revision) 07 Mar 2025			
version 1 07 Oct 2024	 view		

- Irene Kyomuhangi** , Lancaster University, Lancaster, UK
Tulane School of Public Health and Tropical Medicine, New Orleans, USA
- Richard Idro**, Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Kampala, Uganda

Saharan (SSA) countries has increased in the past two decades, PTA plan and practice is underreported or very low.

Objective

To evaluate PTA plan and implementation practice on TB, Malaria and Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) clinical trial studies conducted in the sub-Saharan African countries.

Method

A quantitative, cross-sectional study, using a self-administered online questionnaire was used to evaluate the PTA plans and practices of Principal Investigators (PIs), trial coordinators, and sponsors in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Findings

Nearly half of the study respondents did not provide PTA plans for TB, Malaria, and NTDs in clinical trials. Most of the respondents indicated a need for training on post-trial access.

Conclusion

PTA training should be prepared and facilitated for researchers, IRB members, PIs, funders, and sponsors; discussion and arrangement on PTA should be done before the conduct of the trial; and there should be written agreement between the parties to guarantee PTA to study participants and community after the end of the trial study.

Keywords

post-trial access, clinical trial, TB, Malaria, NTDs

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [European & Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership](#) (EDCTP) gateway.

3. [Okereke Udohchukwu Promise](#) ,

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Corresponding author: Yemisrach Seralegne (yemzeward@gmail.com)

Author roles: **Seralegne Y:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Wangamati CK:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Bernabe RdIC:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Mdala I:** Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Software; **Zewdie M:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Adane HT:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Software, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership programme under grant agreement No CSA2019ERC2680 (Improving post-trial access arrangements in clinical trials in sub-Saharan Africa [AccessAfrica]).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Seralegne Y *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Seralegne Y, Wangamati CK, Bernabe RdIC *et al.* **Post-trial access practice in malaria, tuberculosis, and NTDs clinical trial studies across Sub-Saharan African countries, A quantitative study [version 2; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 1 not approved]** Open Research Europe 2025, 4:212 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18175.2>

First published: 07 Oct 2024, 4:212 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18175.1>

REVISED Amendments from Version 1

In our revised manuscript, we have made several significant improvements to address the reviewers' comments and strengthen our study:

Updated References: We have incorporated recent and relevant articles to support our claims, ensuring that our references are both sufficient and up to date.

Acronym Consistency: All acronyms, including PTA, have been consistently defined and used throughout the manuscript, particularly in the abstract.

Concise Writing: Long sentences have been condensed for clarity and readability.

Detailed Justifications: We have provided thorough justifications for the reviewers' comments, supported by our data.

Enhanced Findings: The research findings have been elaborated to provide a more comprehensive discussion.

Refined Results Section: We have strengthened the results section by incorporating additional details on the study population's characteristics, the PTA plan and arrangements, and the PTA training needs of the study participants.

Streamlined Presentation: Unnecessary graphs and words have been removed to minimize confusion and improve readability.

We appreciate the reviewers' valuable feedback, which has helped us improve the clarity and impact of our manuscript.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Introduction

Background

Clinical trials are research studies performed in people aimed at evaluating a medical, surgical, or behavioral intervention. They are the primary way that researchers find out if a new treatment, like a new drug or diet or medical device (for example, a pacemaker) is safe and effective in people (Vulcano, 2017). A clinical trial is often a clinical trial is used to learn if a new treatment is more effective and/or has less harmful side effects than the standard treatment (NIH, 2023).

Africa is home to 17% of the world's population and carries 25% of the global disease burden (Hwenda *et al.*, 2022). However, it contributes less than 3% of worldwide clinical trials conducted on the continent (Hwenda *et al.*, 2022). Studies have shown that this is mainly due to limited clinical trial capacity, which is attributed to inadequate funding, poor research infrastructure, and a lack of trained personnel, including clinical trialists and laboratory researchers (Vischer, 2016). Furthermore, regulatory challenges, including ethical concerns, significantly hinder the implementation and expansion of clinical trials in Africa (Ndembi *et al.*, 2024). Consequently, PTA practices are not as well established or widespread in Africa compared to other continents. Enhancing clinical trial application and review capabilities in African countries is crucial for revitalizing the continent's role in managing communicable and non-communicable diseases. It significantly improves PTA plans and practices among stakeholders and enhances the region's

preparedness for frequent pandemic onsets (Ogunleye *et al.*, 2020).

Declaration of Helsinki, article 34 PTA states, "In advance of a clinical trial, sponsors, researchers, and host country governments should make provisions for post-trial access for all participants who still need an intervention identified as beneficial in the trial. This information must also be disclosed to participants during the informed consent process." (DoH, 2013). The Declaration of Helsinki has been revised; there is a recent version of 2024 (DoH, 2024). Therefore, PTA should be planned and documented in the study protocol. The execution plan should be reviewed and updated during the clinical trial. PTA has various aspects. First, it refers to providing knowledge and intervention, if any. Second, it refers to the potential beneficiaries, which could be research participants and/or the intended patient group in the community and/or country. Third, PTA provisions for research participants must be free of charge. PTA for the community and/or host country usually comes in the form of availability and accessibility of the medicinal product within a reasonable time. Access to an investigational intervention is justified by the principle of beneficence, "which requires researchers and sponsors to safeguard the health of participants when it is in their power to do so." (CIOMS, 2016) It is also supported by the principle of distributive justice: participants, and by extension, the community or host country, assist researchers in generating valuable data, and, in return, researchers should ensure that participants receive the needed care to safeguard their health.

Even though the number of clinical trials in LMICs has increased dramatically (Van Roessel *et al.*, 2019), most of the trials are funded, sponsored, or otherwise influenced by private or public entities from high-income countries. The lack of PTA introduces the risk of exploiting study participants in low- and middle-income countries who otherwise have limited access to healthcare (Singh *et al.*, 2019). In this case, national ethics committees and the relevant drug regulation agencies must ensure PTA is in place. While there is limited practical experience on PTA in clinical trials in LMICs, the concept of benefit-sharing, which acts as the theoretical foundation of PTA, is firmly stipulated in different international ethical guidelines (Singh *et al.*, 2019). The UNESCO Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights, for example, highlights the duty of benefit-sharing pertaining to scientific and technological innovations, in particular with developing countries (Chirac & Torreele, 2006; UNESCO, 2009).

The Declaration of Helsinki requires the sharing of benefits in medical research with the vulnerable group (DoH, 2013), and the CIOMS International Ethical Guidelines require multi-stakeholder cooperation to make the studied intervention and the knowledge gained available to the population or community (CIOMS, 2016).

Hence, ethical guidelines are clear that PTA, in the form of concrete plans and procedures for benefit-sharing and access (may it be in the form of reasonable pricing of an approved

indication in the host country, free medicinal product for research participants, the provision of knowledge to the relevant patient population and the community), must be intrinsic to clinical trial planning. Despite these ethical guidelines, the general status quo of PTA is not encouraging: the provision of PTA is “rather the exception than the rule” (Jimenez *et al.*, 2019; Schippe, 2015).

In line with the above principles, this manuscript will explore PTA planning and implementation on TB, Malaria, and NTDs clinical trials in Sub-Saharan African countries.

Methods

Study design

The study is a descriptive cross-sectional study. A self-administered online questionnaire was used to explore PTA planning and implementation practices among principal investigators, sponsors, and study coordinators who implemented TB, Malaria, and NTDs clinical trial studies between 2008 and 2019.

The selected studies were conducted between 2008 and 2019 in Sub-Saharan African countries and registered in the Clinical trials.gov or Pan African Clinical Trial Registry (PACTR; tiral.gov). We identified 242 completed clinical trial studies from the registers. From the identified studies, we selected a total of 300 participants and invited them to participate in the study. From the registry, 110 participants were registered as PI and sponsor, 122 were registered as PIs, and 78 were registered as trial coordinators. A total of 37 study participants agreed to participate by filling out the questionnaires. Of the 37 participants, 21 (56.8%) were principal investigators, 4 (10.8%) were sponsors, and 12 (32.4%) were study coordinators. Most participants were based in sub-Saharan African countries (56.8%).

We developed and distributed a survey questionnaire to collect information on the PTA, types, and implementation practices of PIs, Sponsors, and trial coordinators who conducted clinical trials on TB, Malaria, or NTDs across Sub-Saharan Africa based on a literature review of the literature (Cook, 2014).

Study setting

We sought clinical trial studies on Malaria, TB, and NTDs within SSA conducted between 2008 and 2019. We sought these studies in the clinicaltrials.gov and Pan African Clinical Trial Registry.

Sample and sampling strategy

The respondents were principal investigators (PI), Co-PI, sponsors, researchers, and clinical trial coordinators who conducted clinical trial research in TB, Malaria, and NTDs between 2008 and 2019 within sub-Saharan African countries. Purposive sampling was used to select the study sample. The recruitment of study participants entailed sending emails to PIs, co-PIs, sponsors, researchers, and trial coordinators who were involved in clinical trials on Malaria, TB, & NTDs between 2008 and 2019 within Sub-Saharan African countries. These individuals were registered on the clinicaltrials.gov or Pan African Clinical Trial Registry websites. We retrieved their contact information from

the registries and emailed consent forms and questionnaires. Some of the contact information was not useful as some participants had moved on to other organizations, making it difficult to trace them and, as such, limiting the response rate. Only 37 respondents completed the questionnaire. Online surveys are known for poor response rates in low- and middle-income countries due to internet connectivity issues (Nayak & Narayan, 2019).

The search for TB, Malaria, and NTDs clinical trial studies was conducted from November 1, 2021, to January 31, 2022. The keywords used for the study were TB, Malaria, NTDs, trial ID, scientific trial title, disease name, clinical trial start time, completed time, recruitment country, PI contact address, sponsor email address, and 1st author name and address.

Data collection tool and procedures

Based on the research objective, a questionnaire with 17 questions on socio-demographics, PTA knowledge, PTA plans, discussions and arrangements, PTA implementation, stakeholder involvement, trial products, and roles were sent out. The survey questionnaire was pre-tested amongst the Armauer Hansen Research Institute (AHRI) researchers to check if the developed tool is linguistically meaningful, if all necessary questions are asked in the right way, or if any other challenges may have been overseen or undetected during the process of tool development. Afterwards, the questionnaire was distributed to the study participants through their email addresses. Unfortunately, the response rate was low, so we shortened the questionnaire to encourage study participation. The participant responses were stored on the AHRI server.

The shortened questionnaire contained a few questions on (i) socio-demographics, (ii) roles in the conducted clinical trials, (iii) PTA plans, types, and implementation practices, & (iv) the need for PTA training. It was combined with information sheets and consent forms and sent to 300 email addresses.

Data management and analysis

StataSE18 (<https://www.stata.com>) software was used to perform descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies and percentages, on anonymous data to maintain participants confidentiality. The Fisher's exact test assessed the relationship between two categorical variables. The findings are presented in tables and graphically. We considered p-values less than 0.05 as statistically significant. Though we used STATA version 18 software, we shared the dataset with Excel sheet- which can be used to perform similar descriptive analysis, or it can be exported to other freely available statistical software's like R (RStudio Team, 2020). The R- or RStudio software is freely available language and environment for statistical computing and graphics that can be downloaded to most operating systems including Microsoft Windows, Linux, Mac OS, used to replicate the study result. (SCIRP) (<http://www.rstudio.com/>)

Ethical considerations

This study received ethical approval from the Armauer Hansen Research Institute (AHRI) and the All-African Tuberculosis,

Leprosy Treatment, Rehabilitation, and Training Centre Institutional Review Board (AHRI/ALERT IRB) with approval reference number PO/43/20 dated on 21/01/2021. Additionally, the Ministry of Education (MOE) National Ethical Review Board (NERB) of Ethiopia granted approval with reference number MOSHE/RD/04/246/84/21 dated on 10/06/2021. The study also got renewal for approval from the Ministry of Education (MOE) National Ethical Review Committee of Ethiopia with the reference number of MOSHE/RD/03/246/505/22 dated on 08/06/2022. Written informed consent was obtained from all study participants prior to their participation in the study. Within the data collection procedures, the applicant strictly maintained the participant's confidentiality by using the study code number as identification for each participant for anonymity.

Results

Characteristics of the study population

A total of 300 potential participants were invited to complete the survey, 37 participants responded. Themes explored were

trial sites, roles in conducted clinical trials, place of work at the time of the trial, PTA arrangements and discussions and need for PTA training.

The research team identified 242 completed clinical trials on malaria, TB, and NTDs across Sub-Saharan Africa countries. Among these, 114 trials focused on Malaria, 70 on tuberculosis, and 58 on NTDs. These clinical trials were conducted between 2008 and 2019 and were registered on clinical trials.gov or the Pan African clinical trial registry (PACTR).

Table 1 shows the distribution of the study participants and trial sites stratified by PTA arrangement. As shown in the Table 1, thirty-seven study participants completed the survey questionnaires. Out of the 37 study participants, 21 (56.8%) were principal investigators, 4 (10.8%) were sponsors, and 12 (32.4%) were study coordinators. Most of the PIs (57.1%) and sponsors (75.0%) were involved in PTA arrangements, whereas study coordinators were evenly distributed between those who facilitated

Table 1. Distribution of the study participants stratified by PTA arrangement, (N = 37).

	PTA arrangement		Total	P-value
	Yes (n = 21)	No (n = 16)		
Role of the participants				0.72
Principal Investigator (PI)	12 (57.1)	9 (42.9)	21 (56.8)	
Sponsor	3 (75.0)	1 (25.0)	4 (10.8)	
Study co-ordinator	6 (50.0)	6 (50.0)	12 (32.4)	
Need for PTA training				< 0.01
Yes	10 (38.5)	16 (61.5)	26 (70.3)	
No	11 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	11 (29.7)	
Trial sites				
Single-center:				0.94
Burkina Faso	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	3 (8.1)	
Cote d'Ivoire	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	1 (2.7)	
Democratic Republic of Congo	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (5.4)	
Ethiopia	2 (40.0)	3 (60.0)	5 (13.5)	
Ghana	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	3 (8.1)	
Kenya	2 (66.7)	1 (3.3)	3 (8.1)	
Malawi	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	1 (2.7)	
Mozambique	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
Nigeria	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	2 (5.4)	
Senegal	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
South Africa	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
Tanzania	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	1 (2.7)	
Uganda	1 (50.0)	1 (50.0)	2 (5.4)	

	PTA arrangement		Total	¹ P-value
	Yes (n = 21)	No (n = 16)		
Multi-center:				
Benin, Burkina Faso, Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, Malawi, Tanzania, Mali	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
Ethiopia, Kenya, Sudan, Uganda	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
Tanzania, Equatorial Guinea	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
South Africa, Tanzania, Mozambique, The Gambia	0 (0.0)	1 (100.0)	1 (2.7)	
The Gambia, Sierra Leone, Senegal	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
Kenya, Uganda, Mozambique, Rwanda, Mali, Burkina-Faso, Gabon	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
The Gambia, Senegal, Nigeria, and Guinea Conakry	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (2.7)	
²Unknown center (s)	1 (25.0)	3 (75.0)	4 (10.8)	
Trial site by size summarized				0.43
Multi-centered	7 (63.6)	4 (36.4)	11 (29.7)	
Single-centered	14 (53.9)	12 (46.1)	26 (70.3)	

PTA arrangements and those who did not. Twenty-six out of 37 participants (70.3%) indicated that they would like to receive PTA training. Among those who would like to be trained on PTA, 38.5% had facilitated PTA arrangements. Regarding trial sites, 70% conducted single-center clinical trials, whereas 30% carried out multi-center clinical trials across sub-Saharan African countries as illustrated in [Figure 1](#). Six of the seven known multi-center sites participated in PTA arrangements as illustrated in [Table 1](#).

Post-trial access plans and arrangements

Respondents were asked whether they provided PTA plans, conducted discussions, or made arrangements in their clinical trials and, if yes, in what form. As shown in [Figure 2](#), 21 (57%) study participants stated that they provided PTA plans, discussions, or arrangements. [Figure 2](#) illustrates that 9 participants (24.3%) had developed PTA plans or arrangements, while 12 (32.4%) had implemented PTA. However, 16 participants (43%) reported no discussions or arrangements made regarding PTA in clinical trials related to malaria, tuberculosis, or neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) across Sub-Saharan African countries. These findings highlight a significant gap in PTA planning and provision, despite the steady increase in clinical trial studies conducted in the region within the last two decades.

PTA training needs

PTA arrangements involve a process initiated by the sponsor, funder, or host country after the conclusion of a clinical trial to provide access to information or knowledge about the

research, or newly identified drugs, vaccines, or medical devices. PTA training, on the other hand, refers to a short course focusing on planning, types, and implementation of research findings for the community or trial participants after the clinical trial ends. Study participants were asked about their need for PTA training. Twenty-six respondents (70.3%) expressed the need for PTA training, while eleven respondents (29.7%) were not interested as shown in [Table 1](#). Most respondents were keen to learn about PTA planning, arrangements, and implementation. As shown in "[Figure 3](#)," the majority of Principal Investigators (61.9%), sponsors (75%), and study coordinators (83.3%) indicated a desire for PTA training.

Discussion

This is the first study in SSA to explore PTA planning, arrangements, and implementation. The findings are key as they provide a glimpse of PTA, an underexplored concept in clinical trial research within SSA. Although more than half of the clinical trials had PTA plans, about 57.14% had implemented PTA.

These numbers indicate low PTA. However, they are slightly higher than the earlier findings of ([Hellmann et al., 2022](#)), which reported no PTA in LMIC and ([Jimenez et al., 2019](#)) which found that while the majority of clinical trial sponsors declared PTA, a closer examination of their responses revealed that no PTA was provided in the form of access to the medicinal product for research participants, the community, or the host country.

Figure 1. Distribution of the trial study sites, where the trial took place.

Figure 2. Distribution of the responses on PTA plans, discussion or arrangements made.

Institutional Review Board (IRB) members should request PTA plans during the review process of trial documents. The lack of a pan-African (or international) platform to follow up on whether researchers implement their PTA plans once the research is completed makes oversight difficult. In the case of at least some, if not most, of the Sub-Saharan countries, the absence of regulation and follow-up on the implementation process of PTA presents a significant challenge to its feasibility. The challenges related to PTA stem from limited knowledge, mutual agreement, and commitment from those responsible for ensuring the rights, safety, and well-being of study participants and the community.

Addressing these challenges can be achieved through PTA training for researchers, sponsors, and IRB members to update

their perspectives on PTA and to consider it in the protocol development and review process. Active participation of research stakeholders in the planning, process, and implementation of PTA can maximize its feasibility in the region and help ensure the rights and benefits of research participants and their communities or countries.

Strengths and limitations of the study

This is the first study in SSA to explore PTA arrangements and their implementation. The study provides a glimpse into PTA, an under-researched topic in clinical trial research. The limited access to clinical trial vaccines during COVID-19 for LMICs that participated in the research necessitates capacity building on PTA to ensure they benefit from research. This study indicates a gap in clinical research where nearly half of the

Figure 3. Clustered bar graph showing the desire for PTA training.

studies do not provide PTA and a dire need for PTA training. Despite the low response rate from selected study participants, the study contributes to filling a knowledge gap on PTA overview with SSA.

Conclusion and recommendations

PTA training should be offered to research stakeholders to address knowledge gaps in planning, discussions, and arrangements for PTA. National research guidelines should be updated to integrate PTA plans, ensuring fair access to medicinal products for study participants and communities in need. Furthermore, the principles of distributive justice and beneficence underscore the importance of mutual agreements among researchers, funders, sponsors, and host countries to guarantee PTA provision. **This highlights the need for** a collaborative framework where various stakeholders including governments, pharmaceutical companies, and global health organizations contribute to sustainable access solutions. A balanced approach is crucial to fostering innovation while ensuring that trial participants and their communities benefit from research outcomes.

Data availability

The data for this article consists of bibliographic references, which are included in the References section.

Zenodo: Post-trial access practice in Malaria, Tuberculosis, and NTDs Clinical Trial studies in Sub-Saharan African

countries, quantitative study. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13752053>

- Figure 1. Distribution of the trial study sites, where the trial took place.
- Figure 2. Distribution of the responses on PTA plans, discussion or arrangements made.
- Figure 3. Clustered bar graph showing the desire for PTA training.
- Table 1. Distribution of the study participants stratified by PTA arrangement, (N = 37).
- Information sheet for study participants.
- PTA data Excel format.
- Raw data survey 1
- Raw data survey 2
- Study survey questionnaires

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license \(CC-BY 1.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Authors contribution

1. Mrs. Yemisrach Zewdie Seralegne - contributed to design, acquisition of data, analysis, and interpretation of data, wrote the first draft of the manuscript, and revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.

2. Dr. Cynthia Khamala Wangamati - contributed to conception and design, analysis, interpretation of data, reviewing and editing the manuscript critically for important intellectual content.
3. Prof. Rosemarie de la Cruz Bernabe - contributed to conception and design, analysis, and interpretation of data, reviewing and editing the manuscript critically for important intellectual content.
4. Mr. Ibrahim Mdala - contributed to analysis and interpretation of data.
5. Dr. Martha Zewdie - contributed to design, acquisition of data and revised the manuscript for important intellectual content.

6. Dr. Hawult Taye - contributed to design, acquisition of data, analysis, and interpretation of data. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgement

- We would like to acknowledge the EDCTP2 programme for this research financial support.
- We would like to acknowledge Dr. Ewenat Gebrehanna for helping us with recruitment.
- We are grateful to all study participants.
- For the purpose of open access, the author has applied a CC0 BY public copyright license to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising from this submission.

References

- Chirac P, Torreele E: **Global framework on essential health R&D.** *Lancet.* 2006; **367**(9522): 1560–1561.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Cook KJ: **Exploring academic and REB members' attitudes toward post-trial access.** 2014.
[Reference Source](#)
- Council for International Organizations Medical Sciences (CIOMS): **International ethical guidelines for health-related research involving humans.** 2016.
[Reference Source](#)
- Declaration of Helsinki (DoH): **World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects.** *JAMA.* 2013; **310**(20): 2191–4.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Declaration of Helsinki (DoH): **WMA Declaration of Helsinki – ethical principles for medical research involving human participants.** <wma-declaration-of-helsinki.pdf>, 2024.
[Reference Source](#)
- Hellmann F, Bernabe RC, Homedes N: **Post-trial provisions in the Declaration of Helsinki: a watered-down principle that needs to be strengthened.** *J R Soc Med.* 2022; **115**(11): 420–423.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Hwenda L, Sidibe M, Makanga M: **The African medicines agency: the key to unlocking clinical research in Africa.** *Lancet Glob Health.* 2022; **10**(8): e1088–e1089.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Jimenez EB, Virtudazo JMP, Torres CE, et al.: **Availability of Post-Trial Access in clinical trials: a review of clinical trial protocols submitted to the research ethics board of the University of the Philippines Manila.** *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2019; **35**(11): 1849–1855.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Nayak MSDP, Narayan KA: **Strengths and weaknesses of online surveys.** 2019.
[Reference Source](#)
- Ndembi N, Mekonen TT, Folayan MO, et al.: **Strengthening and expanding capacities in clinical trials: advancing pandemic prevention, preparedness and response in Africa.** *Nat Commun.* 2024; **15**(1): 8662.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- NIH: **What are clinical trials and studies?** 2023.
[Reference Source](#)
- Ogunleye OO, Basu D, Mueller D, et al.: **Response to the novel Corona Virus (COVID-19) pandemic across Africa: successes, challenges, and implications for the future.** *Front Pharmacol.* 2020; **11**: 1205.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- PACTR.
[Reference Source](#)
- RStudio Team: **RStudio: integrated development for R.** RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA, 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
- Schippe SCAI: **Post-trial access to treatment: how expanded access may offer a strategic solution.** 2015.
[Reference Source](#)
- SCIRP, R Core Team: **R: A language and environment for statistical computing.** R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2021.
[Reference Source](#)
- Singh H, Rao SV, Kakkar AK, et al.: **Posttrial access to medical interventions: intricacies, challenges, and solutions.** *Int J Appl Basic Med Res.* 2019; **9**(1): 3–8.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- tiral.gov.
[Reference Source](#)
- UNESCO: **The UNESCO universal declaration on bioethics and human rights.** 2009.
[Reference Source](#)
- Van Roessel IMAA, Mazur NI, Shah SK, et al.: **Post-Trial Access in maternal vaccine trials.** *Am J Perinatol.* 2019; **36**(S 02): S41–S47.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Vischer N: **Efficiency and quality in conducting clinical trials in sub-Saharan Africa.** University of Basel, 2016.
[Reference Source](#)
- Vulcano D: **Current events in pre-approval access in the United States.** 2017.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ✖

Version 2

Reviewer Report 08 March 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.21418.r51857>

© 2025 **Kyomuhangi I.** This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

? **Irene Kyomuhangi**

¹ Lancaster, Lancaster University, Lancaster, England, UK

² Tulane School of Public Health and Tropical Medicine, New Orleans, USA

The authors have made a good effort to address the questions raised in the previous round of review. However, there are still some important details that could be improved or are currently lacking.

The abstract lacks crucial information about the study's scope, results, and their generalizability. It does not provide details on sample sizes or any specific quantitative metrics such as numbers, percentages, or other relevant data. As a result, the reliability and generalizability of the study and its findings remain unclear. Simply stating that these details are included in the main text is insufficient; a summary of this information in the abstract is necessary.

Sample and sampling strategy: The authors have still not indicated why a sample size of 300 was selected and invited to participate. Was there a sample size calculation? What informed the 300. Why not select 20, or 200 or 1000? It's also a bit odd to suggest that the response rate was low because "online surveys typically have poor response rates in low- and middle-income countries due to internet connectivity problems." The target group for this study (which is made up of PIs and CoIs and donors, etc) is not likely to be impacted by such connectivity issues.

The updates to Table 1 have improved readability but are still confusing. Please clarify that the figures in brackets represent percentages. Additionally, the denominators for these percentages are not always evident. For instance, in the 'Need for PTA training' section, it is unclear what the denominators for those percentages are.

Having multiple definitions for PTA makes it hard to discern which definition aligns with which outcome. It would be helpful to clearly distinguish between these definitions and specify the corresponding results for each one. Employing more precise language when discussing these terms could improve clarity. For instance, what exactly does the 'PTA arrangement' refer to? Is it a dissemination meeting or workshop? What does 'PTA implementation' involve? And how is this

different from 'PTA arrangement'? The authors sometimes group these terms together, while at other times they use them separately in the paper, leading to confusion. Please either group all these terms together as PTA and state this clearly, or be specific about the distinction between them.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Statistics and epidemiology, malaria, NTDs

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Apr 2025

Yemisrach Seralegne

Responses for the reviewer comments on the PTA V2 manuscript

C1. The abstract lacks crucial information about the study's scope, results, and their generalizability. It does not provide details on sample sizes or any specific quantitative metrics such as numbers, percentages, or other relevant data. As a result, the reliability and generalizability of the study and its findings remain unclear. Simply stating that these details are included in the main text is insufficient; a summary of this information in the abstract is necessary.

R1. We have revised the abstract to include information on the study's scope, results, and generalizability. Kindly see the added highlights in the abstract [section on page 1](#).

C2. Sample and sampling strategy: The authors have still not indicated **why a sample size of 300** was selected and invited to participate. Was there a sample size calculation? What informed the 300. Why not select 20, or 200 or 1000? It's also a bit odd to suggest that the **response rate was low** because "online surveys typically have poor response rates in low- and middle-income countries due to internet connectivity problems." The target group for this study (which is made up of PIs and CoIs and donors, etc) is not likely to be impacted by such connectivity issues.

R2. Thank you for the comment. The selection of 300 participants was based on the number of completed clinical trial studies identified from clinical trial registries (242 studies). From these studies, we compiled a list of relevant stakeholders Principal Investigators (PIs), trial coordinators, and sponsors who were eligible to provide insights into post-trial access (PTA) practices. The final sample size of 300 was determined based on the total number of unique individuals associated with these trials, ensuring a diverse and representative pool of participants across different roles in clinical trial implementation. Kindly, see the explanation on [page 5](#).

○ **Explanation for the Low Response Rate**

Despite our repeated efforts to engage study participants through more than two reminder emails and outreach via social media platforms such as Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter, the response rate remained low, with only 37 out of 300 participants completing the self-administered questionnaire. Kindly see the highlighted text on pages 5 and 6 for an

explanation of why we had a low response rate.

C3. The updates to Table 1 have improved readability but are still confusing. Please clarify that the **figures in brackets represent percentages**. Additionally, **the denominators** for these percentages are not always evident. For instance, in the 'Need for PTA training' section, it is unclear what the denominators for those percentages are.

R3. We acknowledge the concern regarding the clarity of denominators in the 'Need for PTA Training' section. We have adjusted the table, and denominators can be calculated across rows. Kindly see the revised Table **1 on page 8**.

C4. Having multiple definitions for PTA makes it hard to discern which definition aligns with which outcome. It would be helpful to clearly distinguish between these definitions and specify the corresponding results for each one. Employing more precise language when discussing these terms could improve clarity. For instance, what exactly does the 'PTA arrangement' refer to? Is it a dissemination meeting or workshop? What does 'PTA implementation' involve? And how is this different from 'PTA arrangement'? The authors sometimes group these terms together, while at other times they use them separately in the paper, leading to confusion. Please either group all these terms together as PTA and state this clearly or be specific about the distinction between them.

R4. Thank you for the comment. We have provided definitions in the introduction section. Please see the highlighted text **on page 4**.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 06 January 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.19644.r48308>

© 2025 Idro R. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Richard Idro

¹ Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Kampala, Uganda

² Makerere University College of Health Sciences, Kampala, Uganda

First, old or outdated information is used to inform the study. For example, the quote that only 0.025% of registered trials in clinicaltrials.gov come from Africa was a study published in 2014. Similarly, that nearly 50% of African studies are conducted in South Africa is based on a publication over 12 years ago. There could have been a lot of changes since then.

Secondly, it was not clear how a decision was made to invite 300 participants. Was this the

required sample size? If so, the study failed badly as only 37 responses (12%) were obtained. What, therefore, is the validity of these findings? They cannot surely be representative. Moreover, even the 37 responses were based on a shorter version of the study tool, and not the initial tested questionnaire because of the poor response.

Figure 1, which attempts to give the distribution of the respondents' country uses percentages. This gives a wrong perception for such a small number. They should have used the actual numbers. Furthermore, on the validity of the results, what was the distribution of the respondents (responded and based in an African Institution vs responded and based in a non-African Institution) to understand these issues? This comparison is not given.

The methods left out a critical component: the investigators did not provide a standardized definition or criteria of what PTA in this context is. This was left for the respondents to figure out. It is unlikely that the responses all meant the same thing. Thus, the results are presented in non-uniform manner.

Potentially, the ability to provide post-trial care as such is more difficult with the PI, co-PI and study coordinators than sponsors especially if these are Pharmaceutical companies. Unfortunately, only 4 of the respondents were companies. First, what proportion out of the 300 approached were companies? Was this representative? Secondly, were the 4/37 who responded similar? Could more have provided PTA if more pharmaceutical companies provided answers?

The results section is grossly inadequate but is understandable because of the small numbers. This study could have further been strengthened with a qualitative component.

The whole concept of PTA and the responsibilities of the different actors need to be re-examined. Many studies in Africa are investigated, and funding is sought from foundations and scientific grants or fellowships. It is grossly unfair to imagine that such should put in plans for free post-trial distribution or differential pricing, which is beyond their scope. Such a scenario can even kill innovations.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

No

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Paediatrics, Child Health, Paediatric Neurology, Clinical trials

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Reviewer Report 13 November 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.19644.r45749>

© 2024 Kyomuhangi I. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Irene Kyomuhangi

¹ Lancaster, Lancaster University, Lancaster, England, UK

² Tulane School of Public Health and Tropical Medicine, New Orleans, USA

³ Lancaster, Lancaster University, Lancaster, England, UK

⁴ Tulane School of Public Health and Tropical Medicine, New Orleans, USA

The authors of this paper seek to evaluate the planning and implementation of post-trial access for clinical trials related to TB, Malaria, and Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) in sub-Saharan Africa. Post-trial access is an important part of project management that requires careful planning and fair execution. The authors should be commended for their work on this paper. However, improving the way they present and explain their research would make it stronger. They also need to be clearer about their methods and results. The paper should be revised to correct grammar and spelling mistakes and include proper references to back up their claims, especially in the 'Background' section. It's also unclear which sub-Saharan countries are part of the clinical trials included in this study, when the searches for the clinical trials took place, and what specific terms were used in those searches. It's not clear if the findings can be applied to all sub-Saharan Africa or if they represent current information.

Specific comments:

1. Title: Please consider re-phrasing the title to add... 'a quantitative study' at the end.

Abstract:

1. There are several acronyms in the abstract that haven't been defined. Please provide definitions for these upon their first use (e.g., CIOMS, TB, NTD, PI, IRB).
2. Introduction -> The introduction contains relatively long sentences. Please consider condensing this section to allow for more content in the rest of the abstract.
3. Objective -> Please ensure that the beginning of each sentence is capitalized (this applies to the 'Method' and 'Finding' subsections as well). Additionally, please specify which sub-

Saharan countries are being referred to.

4. Method -> The current description is inadequate. Please provide detailed information about the quantitative methods employed and the sample sizes for each group. For instance, "We designed a questionnaire to gather information on X [list key themes]. A total of X[number of] respondents participated, including X[number of] PIs, X[number of] coordinators, etc."
5. Finding -> The information provided in this section is insufficient. Please elaborate on the findings, specifying which themes were the most common or significant. Were these themes consistent across all surveyed groups?

Background: The major comment for this section is to provide sufficient evidence/references for the claims made, particularly about the state of clinical trials in sub-Saharan countries.

1. In the third paragraph, the phrase "clinical trials in Africa are considered to be in their embryonic stages" is somewhat unclear. Does this refer to the quantity or the scale of the clinical trials being conducted in African nations? Furthermore, the citation used to support this statement is over seven years old—are there any more recent statistics available?
2. In the fourth paragraph, kindly cite the original source from which the 47.3% figure originates, along with the date it was calculated, since it is over 10 years old. Additionally, it would be helpful to clarify what is meant by a "well-developed health system." At this point, it is also unclear why the authors have specifically chosen to emphasize South Africa and Ethiopia.
3. In the fifth and sixth paragraphs, please ensure consistency in the definition of Post-trial access (PTA). In the fifth paragraph, PTA is described as "the ethical imperative," while in the sixth paragraph, it is characterized as "the provision of both knowledge and intervention" and refers to "potential beneficiaries." This inconsistency makes the definition of PTA as used by the authors somewhat ambiguous.
4. In the seventh paragraph, kindly provide references for the quotations included.
5. In the ninth paragraph, please provide references to support the assertions made, such as the claim that "there is limited practical experience on PTA in clinical trials in LMICs."

Methods:

1. This section would benefit from a clearer definition of the variables and the reasoning behind the authors' categorization, particularly those listed in Table 1: Regarding the 'lead institute' variable, the term 'Partners' in the 'Pharmaceutical company/Partners' category is vague—could the authors provide clarification? Additionally, does the lead institute refer to the participant's current location or their location during the clinical trial? What if the participant was affiliated with an associate institute or organization rather than the lead institute? Regarding the 'funder' variable, can the authors explain the decision to categorize funders as just 'LSHTM' and 'Others'? This could be due to the nature of the data, but greater transparency would be appreciated. Does the 'origin' variable pertain to the participant's place of origin, their current location, or the location they were associated with during the clinical trial? Please clarify. What does 'PTA arrangement' specifically entail? Does it refer to a planned PTA, an implemented PTA plan, or the manner of implementation of the PTA plan? What does 'PTA training' specifically refer to—does it mean a course or workshop?
2. In the study design section, the phrase 'Cross-sectional surveys were used...' implies multiple surveys—were there indeed several, and if so, could you provide an explanation?
3. In the sample and sampling strategy section, please revise the phrase 'namely called' and include references to the databases used (a website would suffice). Additionally, specify

when the search was conducted, which keywords or combinations were employed in the searches, and clarify why an initial sample size of 300 was chosen.

4. In the data collection and procedure section, please define AHRI upon its first mention.
5. In the data management and analysis section, it's unnecessary to state: 'Although we used STATA version 18 software, we shared the dataset with Excel...' Furthermore, what do the authors mean by 'The Fisher's exact test was used to assess the associations between categorical variables'? What exactly do the authors mean by 'associations' in this context?

Results:

1. This section could benefit from the inclusion of a table showing the search results, detailing the number of trials found and their distribution among TB, Malaria, and NTDs, among other categories.
2. For Table 1, please refer to the first comment regarding the 'methods' section. Could you clarify what the p-values signify for lead institute, funder, origin, and site (i.e., what significant differences are being referenced, and how do these relate to the study's objectives)?
3. Regarding Figure 2, is this indicating the location of the participants? Where they were based during the clinical trial? Where the trial itself took place? Additionally, how does this relate to the research question?
4. For post-trial access plans and arrangements, it may be more effective to categorize this data more succinctly if possible—such as 'PTA plan/arrangement', 'PTA implementation', and 'no PTA'—to provide a clearer overview of engagement levels with PTA. This ties back to how the authors are defining PTA.
5. In the section on PTA training needs, the authors focus on participants' willingness to receive training rather than assessing their actual training requirements.

Discussion:

1. The conclusion that 'The challenges related to PTA stem from a lack of knowledge, mutual agreement, and commitment from those responsible for ensuring the rights, safety, and well-being of study participants and the community.' is not supported by the evidence presented in this paper. Specifically in Figure 4, more than half of respondents indicated some plan for, or implementation of PTA

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.**Reviewer Expertise:** Statistics and epidemiology, malaria, NTDs

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Author Response 24 Feb 2025

Yemisrach Seralegne**(1st) Reviewer comment and point by point response *Specific comments:***

C1. Title: Please consider re-phrasing the title to add... ‘; a quantitative study’ at the end.

R1. Thanks for the suggestion. We have addressed this comment on page 1. Please, see the research title.

Abstract:

C1. There are several acronyms in the abstract that haven't been defined. Please provide definitions for these upon their first use (e.g., CIOMS, TB, NTD, PI, IRB).

R1. Thank you for the comment. We have addressed the comment on page 1 paragraph 1 line 1, paragraph 4 line 2, paragraph 5 line 2, and paragraph 7 line 1.

C2. Introduction -> The introduction contains relatively long sentences. Please consider condensing this section to allow for more content in the rest of the abstract.

R2• Thank you for the comment. As requested, the introduction part used to have condensed sentences now. Kindly see page 2, paragraphs 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6.

C3. Objective -> Please ensure that the beginning of each sentence is capitalized (this applies to the ‘Method’ and ‘Finding’ subsections as well). Additionally, please specify which sub-Saharan countries are being referred to.

R3• The beginning of each sentence has been capitalized in the objective, method, and findings subsections as advised. In this study all sub-Saharan African countries are included.

C4. Method -> The current description is inadequate. Please provide detailed information about the quantitative methods employed and the sample sizes for each group. For instance, "We designed a questionnaire to gather information on X [list key themes]. A total of X [number of] respondents participated, including X [number of] PIs, X [number of] coordinators, etc."

R4• Detail description about the quantitative method and sample size is provided on page 4, paragraph 1,3,4 and 5 line 94 to 97, and 101 to 111.

C5. Finding -> The information provided in this section is insufficient. Please elaborate on the findings, specifying which themes were the most common or significant. Were these themes consistent across all surveyed groups?

R5. The most common themes were identified and the findings were elaborated on page 5, paragraph 2, line 160 to 175.

Background: The major comment for this section is to provide sufficient evidence/references for the claims made, particularly about the state of clinical trials in sub-Saharan countries.

R6. Sufficient and updated references have been used throughout the document.

C1. In the third paragraph, the phrase "clinical trials in Africa are considered to be in their embryonic stages" is somewhat unclear. Does this refer to the quantity or the scale of the clinical trials being conducted in African nations? Furthermore, the citation used to support this statement is over seven years old—are there any more recent statistics available?

R1 • We have deleted this sentence and used more recent statistics as advised. Kindly, see references on page 2, paragraph 2 to 4, and line 40 to 54.

C2. In the fourth paragraph, kindly cite the original source from which the 47.3% figure originates, along with the date it was calculated, since it is over 10 years old. Additionally, it would be helpful to clarify what is meant by a "well-developed health system." At this point, it is also unclear why the authors have specifically chosen to emphasize South Africa and Ethiopia.

R2 • We have deleted the whole sentence. The content of the whole paragraph has been updated, and recent research cited results are used as a reference. Kindly see page 2, paragraphs 2, 3, and 4.

C3. In the fifth and sixth paragraphs, please ensure consistency in the definition of post-trial access (PTA). In the fifth paragraph, PTA is described as "the ethical imperative," while in the sixth paragraph, it is characterized as "the provision of both knowledge and intervention" and refers to "potential beneficiaries." This inconsistency makes the definition of PTA as used by the authors somewhat ambiguous.

R3 • PTA is defined consistently throughout the manuscript. on page 2 paragraph 4, and line 51 to 54.

C4. In the seventh paragraph, kindly provide references for the quotations included.

R4 • Reference for the quotations sentence is included on page 3 paragraph 1 and line 64.

C5. In the ninth paragraph, please provide references to support the assertions made, such as the claim that "there is limited practical experience on PTA in clinical trials in LMICs."

R5 • References is put to support the assertions made on page 3 paragraph 2 and line 67-70.

Methods: This section would benefit from a clearer definition of the variables and the reasoning behind the authors' categorization, particularly those listed in **Table 1: C1**.

Regarding the 'lead institute' variable, the term 'Partners' in the 'Pharmaceutical company/Partners' category is vague—could the authors provide clarification?

R1. Thank you, based on the given comments we remove the term from the table 1. Which is helpful to minimize bias and transfer a clear message and ideas to the readers on PTA based on the general objective of the study.

C2. Please clarify. What does 'PTA arrangement' specifically entail? Does it refer to a planned PTA, an implemented PTA plan, or the manner of implementation of the PTA plan? What does 'PTA training' specifically refer to—does it mean a course or workshop?

R2. 'PTA arrangement' term is well clarified in page 7, paragraph 4, line 209 to 211 and PTA training on line 212 to 213

C3. In the study design section, the phrase 'Cross-sectional surveys were used...' implies multiple surveys—were there indeed several, and if so, could you provide an explanation?

R3. It is typing error; we used one survey and corrected.

C4. In the sample and sampling strategy section, please revise the phrase 'namely called' and include references to the databases used (a website would suffice). Additionally, specify when the search was conducted, which keywords or combinations were employed in the searches, and clarify why an initial sample size of 300 was chosen.

R4. Why 300 sample size is clarified well on page 4, paragraph 3 line 100 to 104. When the search was conducted, and key words employed in the searches is clarified now on page 4, paragraph 4.

C5. In the data collection and procedure section, please define AHRI upon its first mention.

R5• AHRI is defined now on page 4, paragraph 5 line 3 to 4.

C6. In the data management and analysis section, it's unnecessary to state: 'Although we used STATA version 18 software, we shared the dataset with Excel...' Furthermore, what do the authors mean by 'The Fisher's exact test was used to assess the associations between categorical variables'? What exactly do the authors mean by 'associations' in this context?

R6• Noted well and corrected. The fisher's exact test ¹Fisher's exact *P*-value showing the association between the role of the participants, PTA training and trial site with PTA arrangements. For example, the association between role and PTA arrangements has a *P* = 0.72. This means that the PIs, sponsors and study coordinators were equally likely to make PTA arrangements.

Results:

C1. This section could benefit from the inclusion of a table showing the search results, detailing the number of trials found and their distribution among TB, Malaria,

and NTDs, among other categories.

R1 • one paragraph was prepared and included to show the search result on page 6, paragraph 2 and line 172 to 175.

C2. For Table 1, please refer to the first comment regarding the 'methods' section. Could you clarify what the p-values signify for lead institute, funder, origin, and site (i.e., what significant differences are being referenced, and how do these relate to the study's objectives)?

R2. The P-Values have been explained under the revised Table 1. Please note that variables like the lead institute and funder have been removed because this information was sourced from the trial registry, not the survey. The term origin has been revised to trial site for better comprehension.

C3. Regarding Figure 2, is this indicating the location of the participants? Where were they based during the clinical trial? Where the trial itself took place? Additionally, how does this relate to the research question?

R3 • We apologize for the lack of clarity. The location of the participants is the place where the trial itself took place, as we tried to identify the PTA practice across the sub-Saharan African countries. Consequently, it was important to know the locations of the trials.

C4. For post-trial access plans and arrangements, it may be more effective to categorize this data more succinctly if possible—such as 'PTA plan/arrangement', 'PTA implementation', and 'no PTA'—to provide a clearer overview of engagement levels with PTA. This ties back to how the authors are defining PTA.

R4. Thanks for the suggestion, this has been amended as requested in figure 2.

C5. In the section on PTA training needs, the authors focus on participants' willingness to receive training rather than assessing their actual training requirements.

R5. We focused on the need for PTA training not willingness. We apologize for the poor grammar.

Discussion:

C1. The conclusion that 'The challenges related to PTA stem from a lack of knowledge, mutual agreement, and commitment from those responsible for ensuring the rights, safety, and well-being of study participants and the community.' is not supported by the evidence presented in this paper. Specifically in Figure 4, more than half of respondents indicated some plan for, or implementation of PTA

R1. **Thanks for the comment, we have revised our conclusion accordingly.**

(2nd) Reviewer comments and point by point responses C1. First, old or outdated information is used to inform the study. For example, the quote that only 0.025% of registered trials in clinicaltrials.gov come from Africa was a study published in 2014. Similarly, that nearly 50% of African studies are conducted in South Africa is based on a publication over 12 years ago. There could have been a lot of changes since then. **R1. Thanks, we accepted the comment and include updated information and reference now.**

C2. Secondly, it was not clear how a decision was made to invite 300 participants. Was this the required sample size? If so, the study failed badly as only 37 responses (12%) were obtained. What, therefore, is the validity of these findings? They cannot surely be representative.

Moreover, even the 37 responses were based on a shorter version of the study tool, and not the initial tested questionnaire because of the poor response.

R2. Thanks, how a decision was made to invite 300 participants is clarified on page 4 paragraph 1. As we retrieve clinical trial studies conducted within 2008-to-2019-time frame, some of the contact information was not useful as some participants had moved on to other organizations, making it difficult to trace them and as such contributed to limiting the response rate.

C3. Figure 1, which attempts to give the distribution of the respondents' country uses percentages. This gives a wrong perception for such a small number. They should have used the actual numbers. Furthermore, on the validity of the results, what was the distribution of the respondents (responded and based in an African Institution vs responded and based in a non-African Institution) to understand these issues? This comparison is not given.

R3. We revise figure 1. Based on the comments given by the reviewers and the general objective of this study. We used the actual number to give a clear perception on the proportion of each participated country.

C4. The methods left out a critical component: the investigators did not provide a standardized definition or criteria of what PTA in this context is. This was left for the respondents to figure out. It is unlikely that the responses all meant the same thing. Thus, the results are presented in non-uniform manner.

R4. We included a standard definition for PTA based on international research guideline references on page1, paragraph 1 and page 2, paragraph 4.

C5. Potentially, the ability to provide post-trial care as such is more difficult with the PI, co-PI and study coordinators than sponsors especially if these are pharmaceutical companies. Unfortunately, only 4 of the respondents were companies. First, what proportion out of the 300 approached were companies? Was this representative? Secondly, were the 4/37 who responded similar? Could more have provided PTA if more pharmaceutical companies provided answers?

R5. Providing PTA to trial study participants and communities is not solely the responsibility of sponsors or pharmaceutical companies; rather, it is the responsibility of all research stakeholders. Detail description on proportion of study participants is briefly written on page 4 paragraph 1.

C6. The results section is grossly inadequate but is understandable because of the small numbers. This study could have further been strengthened with a qualitative component.

R6. We have strengthened the results section of this document by incorporating details on the study population's characteristics, the PTA plan and arrangements, and the PTA training needs of study participants.

C7. The whole concept of PTA and the responsibilities of the different actors need to be re-

examined. Many studies in Africa are investigated, and funding is sought from foundations and scientific grants or fellowships. It is grossly unfair to imagine that such should put in plans for free post-trial distribution or differential pricing, which is beyond their scope. Such a scenario can even kill innovations.

R7. Yes, Re-examining the concept of PTA and the responsibilities of different actors is indeed important to ensure a fair and sustainable approach. While many studies in Africa rely on funding from foundations, scientific grants, or fellowships, expecting them to implement free post-trial distribution or differential pricing may not always be feasible. However, this highlights the need for a collaborative framework where multiple stakeholders—including governments, pharmaceutical companies, and global health organizations—contribute to sustainable access solutions. A balanced approach is essential to support innovation while ensuring that trial participants and communities benefit from the research outcomes.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.